

WASTE REDUCTION, A CATALYST FOR PROFITABILITY FOR A COMPOSITES FABRICATOR

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ABSTRACT

Arjay Technologies in Largo, Florida, is a well-established contract producer of laminates. Currently the company is focusing on offering its expertise and lamination technology to others in the industry. The success Arjay achieved in improving productivity began during the late eighties when the company reexamined its manufacturing methods and techniques to reduce waste and improve profitability. They started by examining the manufacturing system's ability to convert materials and labor into finished product. The company entered into a wall-to-wall analysis that required them to totally rethink the lamination process. Arjay's experience indicates that the typical laminating operation, one that uses gel coat, sprays resin, and lays in reinforcement can cut its costs by as much as 24% through reengineering the laminating operation to reduce waste in design, materials, and labor.

INTRODUCTION

Arjay sells fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) to assemblers and marketers in the boating industry. During the later part of the eighties Arjay struggled as did most companies in the industry to make gains in productivity and profitability. As a result, Arjay reengineered its approach to lamination and found that a laminating operation can cut its costs significantly. The company has now begun offering its expertise and lamination technology to others in the industry. However, before this change in emphasis occurred Arjay made full use of the technologies and methods it is now helping other companies put to use.

Because of Arjay's total focus on FRP, the company is a true cost center for lamination. Consequently, the company's work provides a clear indication of the impact these changes can make on a laminating operation's performance. To achieve these improvements one has to begin by rethinking what is fast, expensive, and wasteful. The result of this rethinking at Arjay Technologies ultimately made the company more competitive.

INITIAL RESULTS OF CHANGE

Initially the changes caused by reengineering looked as if the company was going to increase costs instead of improving profitability. The cost of materials and labor for the laminating operation went up significantly. The average cost increase by category is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Material Cost Increases

Percentage Increase	Category
10%	Gel coat, cost per pound.
40%	Fiberglass, cost per pound. Largely due to the change to knitted fabrics.
7%	Resin, cost per pound.
28%	Increase in the time required to create a laminate due to the use of resin rollers.
37%	Hourly cost for labor. This occurred because Arjay reduced their work force letting the least experienced people go which raised the average plant wage rate.

When a company is committed to trying to break a manufacturing paradigm, many of the gauges for financial performance may show that their beginning efforts are making things worse. Initial indicators often show that a marginally profitable operation is on its way to being unprofitable. The reason this occurs is that most manufacturers use some form of standard costing to determine product profitability. The result is companies see cost reduction as the only way to improve profitability. Voluntary cost increases in material and labor under this system would be avoided. Consequently, this paradigm causes organizations to adopt tactics that are narrowly focused on the price reduction of individual material and labor elements. Cost cutting, however, is unable to optimize the manufacturing system. At Arjay the changes made were based on the performance of the total manufacturing process which provided many more opportunities to improve profitability than cost cutting. Their approach resulted in productivity improvements on a per product basis such as:

- Gel coat was reduced by 50%. Gel coat usage was cut in half by changing the process to provide more uniform thickness.
- Resin was reduced by 54%. Resin was reduced by over half by achieving higher glass ratios and wasting less resin.
- Waste was reduced by 90%. This resulted from reduced materials usage, instituting good material handling practices, and eliminating wasteful manufacturing methods and techniques.
- Work force was reduced by 30%. The manufacturing methods allowed Arjay to reduce its manufacturing work force by 30% while it turned out the same quantity of work.
- Total cost of production dropped by 24%. This was the net result from all the changes put into effect.

THE FRP PARADIGM

To achieve these improvements in productivity Arjay focused on material and waste minimization. Like most manufacturers, Arjay had always been concerned with material usage and scrap. These concerns, however, were dealt with in the context of continuing to spray resin and gel coat with conventional high pressure, high output equipment. The characteristics of this FRP paradigm are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Production Characteristics Before

Resin Application:	Spray Gun
Gel Coat Thickness:	18-20 MILS
Glass to Resin Ratio:	26%
Solvent Type Used:	Volatile, Acetone
Lamination Room Environment:	Dirty, High Maintenance

Spraying resin, applying thick gel coat, employing glass ratios below 30%, using acetone, and operating in a dirty, high maintenance environment creates a production system that places a manufacturer in a financial "grid" or paradigm that limits the profit that can be realized from a business. This type of manufacturing system existed at Arjay for about ten years before they changed. During that time material, labor, and operating expenses as a proportion of sales varied only slightly. A model profit and loss statement for the period is portrayed in Table 3.

Table 3. Profit and Loss Statement for the Old Manufacturing System

Sales	\$100
Material	38
Labor	18
Operating Expense	8
Prime Profit	\$36

As you can see, for every \$100 of sales; material costs were 38%; labor costs, including workman's' compensation, medical, vacations, holidays, etc., were 18%; and operating costs, including utilities, solvents, supplies, maintenance items, etc., were about 8%; leaving a prime profit of 36%. Fixed costs which would be subtracted from prime profit to calculate gross profit are not shown.

BASIS FOR CHANGE

As a contract producer selling component parts to boat builders and marketers, Arjay has no assembly costs or other post FRP part costs to cloud the analysis of its performance as a laminating operation. Consequently, a profit and loss analysis is useful for evaluating the impact these changes will have on a FRP process. Since the major changes were in materials, the biggest expense category in the profit and loss statement, it's useful to examine where the money is spent and how much of the purchased material finds its way to the finished part, see Table 4.

Table 4. Material Usage and Costs

Materials Required to Produce a \$100 Part				
	Purchase Weight	Part Weight	\$/Pound	Purchase Cost
Gel	5	2	\$1.00	\$ 5.00
Glass	12	9	1.00	12.00
Resin	<u>35</u>	<u>20</u>	0.60	<u>21.00</u>
Total	52 Lbs.	31 Lbs.		\$38.00

The left hand column in Table 4 shows that 5 pounds of gel coat, 12 pounds of glass, and 35 pounds of resin for a total of 52 pounds were purchased to make a part that sells for \$100. However, the second column shows that only 31 pounds (60%) of the 52 pounds purchased actually made it into the part. The other 21 pounds (40%) that was purchased became trim scraps, emission losses, over-spray, cutouts, scrap parts, and other forms of waste. Note that the gross or overall glass ratio (excluding the gel coat) is 26% (12 out of 12 + 35), although the finished part had a 31% glass ratio (9 out of 20 + 9).

All of these figures came from a material balance study of the lamination operation. This type of analysis is also referred to as a sources and uses study. The purpose of this type of study is to determine how efficient the laminating operation is in converting purchased materials to product -- Arjay's system was only 60% efficient. Knowing the material conversion efficiency is a good first step for defining the performance of a company's manufacturing system.

From this study it is apparent that the resin supplier is the significant vendor in terms of dollars. The moneys sent to resin companies exceed the amount sent to the glass suppliers by a ratio of 21 to 12. This means that if a tanker of resin costs \$21,000 you would spend only \$12,000 for the glass to go with it. The gel coat cost is less than one fourth the resin cost and consequently, ranks last in the material cost categories. These comparisons and rankings are useful for establishing priorities for changing the system.

Now, let's look at the labor portion of the profit and loss statement. For each \$100 of sales at Arjay there is \$18 of labor cost. The average hourly wage at the time of the study was \$8.00 per hour. This amount includes direct labor such as laminators and gel coaters as well as QC people, warehouse people, maintenance people, and supervision. The average hourly wage for the manufacturing system can be calculated by dividing the gross payroll by the total hours worked for the period. However, the number that is really needed is the percentage of labor in each sales dollar. This can be found by taking the gross wages and dividing them by the total sales. In the profit and loss statement in Table 3 the number is actually the wages per each \$100 of sales for the period. It is extremely important to understand that this total labor represents all people involved in manufacturing since one of the major benefits from reengineering comes from reducing the necessity for staffing the non-value adding positions required by the current laminating system.

The national average for labor cost is reported to be around 10%. Arjay's labor costs (18% of sales) were nearly twice the national average and this labor has significant control over the quantity of materials and supplies used in the manufacturing operation. In many cases, a worker can easily use half again the quantity of materials and supplies that might be required by the

“engineering design” to do the job. Thus open molding can be seen to be an extremely labor intensive and labor dependent activity.

A key part of the reengineering effort was eliminating wasted labor and material. This began by examining the manufacturing process in an effort to determine how labor is utilized. Bettering the utilization of labor requires an understanding of the basics of productivity, especially as it applies to laminating processes. A key concept is productive work (PW). PW occurs when value is added to a product. Of the dozens of tasks that workers routinely carried out at Arjay, most fell into the category of non-productive work (NPW). Some examples of NPW are: mil gauging, cleaning equipment, running flow tests, moving material carts, blowing dust off a mold, and figuring out how to repair a problem. In the vast majority of FRP operations the amount of productive work in a shift is less than 50% of the available labor hours. Therefore, the potential for reducing labor waste is not in trying to make people work faster but to facilitate their working on productive tasks. Since workers have significant control over the amount of materials and supplies going into a product then this aspect must also be factored into the changes that need to be made. Because material costs are more than double the labor cost, there is a tendency to believe that the real benefits are to be realized by directly focusing on material reduction projects. However, the fact that that typically less than half of the laminating labor is productive suggests that there is a major problem with the basic processes.

Another aspect in reengineering the lamination operation is giving the people involved in productive work the control they need. Management has been reluctant to recognize the control that the FRP laminators must have to do their job. If managers insist on running the traditional Manager/Supervisor/Crew Chief/Worker hierarchy, the organization will have difficulty breaking the paradigm. Management must change its emphasis from directing and controlling people to controlling the process. Webster defines “process” as “a series of actions or operations leading to an end.” Thus, all the various productive and nonproductive activities that are carried out constitute your process. Normally it is the process, not lazy workers, that creates non productive work. The exact process (resin rollers, infusion, etc.) that any given lamination operation should use will require considerable study and be very specific to each situation. More and more FRP operations will elect multiple processes as no single one will be able to meet quality levels, productivity requirements, and OSHA/EPA regulations. Chop, spray wet-out, and gel coat spraying are very generic processes. This is why FRP operations use them so much. It is also why they are so wasteful. Most laminating operations will have to consider other processes that are more of a rifle shot in nature. Once the management approach and the basic processes have been defined there are five specific efforts that can make a dramatic impact on productivity.

Resin reduction

In most operations, labor is directly proportional to resin usage. The application of two gallons of resin will take twice as long as one gallon of resin. However, this is not strictly true with fiberglass. It takes just as long to place a heavyweight glass material on the product being built as it does a lighter weight one. However, the heavier weight materials result in higher glass ratios, requiring proportionally less resin. The result -- reduced resin consumption, increased glass usage, and less time required for applying resin. This change to higher glass content provides opportunities for utilizing a slower application device (such as a resin roller) without necessarily sacrificing overall product output. Once the slower application device is in operation and labor utilization starts to increase, other benefits can be realized such as:

- Less styrene flashing off to the air.
- Less material wasted on the floor.
- Lower styrene content resins can be introduced.

Stress Cleanliness

Cleaning up takes a lot of nonproductive time. Design the process so things don't get dirty. This means that cleaner processes, even if they appear to be slower, may well be more productive since they don't create nonproductive cleanup activities.

Broaden Jobs

Make everybody a laminator. Many FRP operations have turned the laminating operation into a collection of crafts such as *Resin Sprayer*, *Kit Maker* or *Laminate Roller*. These people are involved in productive work only for the time their craft is required. Eliminate the craft system and replace it with a single job category, Laminator. Make sure the laminating job is clean and well paid since this is the most critical task in a FRP operation and rich in productive work.

Cut Crew Sizes

If everyone is a laminator then the tools change during the laminating operation, not the people. With broader job responsibilities there is no need to include specialists in the crew. Consequently, the crew can be cut to two or three people who all have the same opportunities to engage in productive work.

Training

Set aside an hour every week for training. This represents 2.5% of the work week devoted to nonproductive work. However, this 2.5% provides a company with an ongoing means to train their laminators and help them develop problem solving skills aimed at reducing the other forms of nonproductive work, excessive material usage, and the large amount of repair and rework that exists in the FRP operation.

How and what should an organization do to train its people? If you can develop lesson plans that are relevant and interesting then focus on cross-training and correcting deficiencies in skills. You can go to industry associations for specific programs on materials and processes. Generic training programs on problem identification and problem solving methods are also available. Focusing on problem solving provides an organization with a means to bootstrap a training program. However, if worse comes to worse don't worry about specific content, train on virtually anything. The statement you are making and the attention you are giving to your workers is far more important to your productivity than the content. Don't let your concerns and worries about teaching hold you back on getting started.

ARJAY'S EXPERIENCE

Reducing waste in Arjay's FRP laminating process involved all of what has been described. Prior to these changes Arjay's typical practice for hand lay-up centered on a spray wet-out operation using 1 1/2 ounce mat and 24 ounce woven roving. After the change the laminating crew used 3/4 ounce mat and knitted fabric. The resin application equipment changed too. The company replaced the spray guns with roller applicators. The changeover to rollers began on the simpler shaped hulls, then moved on to include complex decks and liners. The change in resin formulation, application equipment, and glass resulted in a reengineered lamination operation.

In brief, here is what Arjay Technologies did to change their operation. They started with the resin by changing the chemistry and the way it was stored and dispensed in the plant. The new resin included an extender, had a higher reactivity, and was more viscous due to reduced styrene content. Arjay promoted the resin themselves instead of having the supplier do it. They also installed a temperature controlled bulk storage and recirculation system that looped the entire plant. The catalyst, MEKP, was also circulated to each mixing unit in the plant. The result was a resin that gave predictable performance and worked well with the new lay-up methods.

Although the changes in the resin were important, there were other factors that contributed to Arjay's waste reduction and improvements in financial performance. The reengineered system included:

- A Gel coat spraying operation that was brought into control through the application of **process control techniques**. This allowed Arjay to reduce the amount of gel coat sprayed in two ways. First they were able to eliminate the excessive gel coat thickness that resulted from a highly variable process and second because of the reduction in variability of the process they were able to get consistent results at the lower end of the range for gel coat thickness. The use of a low pressure spray system also helped to improve transfer efficiencies and operator control.
- Resin spraying was eliminated with the introduction of internally fed **resin roller applicators**. These applicators apply resin more uniformly without over spray. Because the resin is not atomized, the applicators significantly reduce styrene loss to the air and maintain a much cleaner work area. Equipment maintenance is reduced because of lower fluid pressures needed by the simpler resin roller system. Solvent usage is also reduced and can be further reduced through the use of a closed system to flush and clean the roller equipment.
- Glass ratios were increased through the **use of knitted and specialized glass fabrics**. The result was an increase in the glass to resin ratio to 38%. The increase in this ratio was also due to some laminate engineering and the benefits that can be realized through the application of resin with the roller system.
- A high boiling point **solvent is sparingly used**. Acetone was eliminated and not seriously missed because of the cleaner resin application methods implemented.
- The operation became noticeably cleaner and required **significantly less maintenance**. This can be attributed largely to the changes in resin and gel coat application processes.

The full impact of the changes to the manufacturing system is apparent by comparing the changes in the materials used after reengineering to the materials required to make the original 31 pound part (Table 5). The results show that the total material cost (\$38) dropped to \$27.54, a reduction of nearly 28%. The part weight also went down by 16%. This reduction in weight is the result of changes in both the manufacturing technology and part design. Savings also showed up in labor and operating expense. The labor cost dropped slightly to \$17 from \$18 and the operating expense was cut in half to \$4.

Table 5. Material Comparisons

	Before				After			
	Lbs. Purch.	Part Weight	\$/Lbs.	Total Cost	Lbs. Purch.	Part Weight	\$/Lbs.	Total Cost
Gel	5	2	1.00	\$5.00	3	2	1.10	\$3.30
Glass	12	9	1.00	12.00	10	9	1.40	14.00
Resin	<u>35</u>	<u>20</u>	0.60	<u>21.00</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>15</u>	0.64	<u>10.24</u>
Total	52	31		\$38.00	29	26		\$27.54
wasted	40 % of purchased materials wasted				10 % of purchased materials			

SUMMARIZING

These changes in manufacturing resulted in making Arjay's glass vender the major supplier. The dollars going towards the purchase of glass were 40% more than the amount spent with the resin supplier. The gel coat cost as a percentage of glass also went down significantly from 42% to 21%. Table 6 compares costs on a unit of measure basis to the cost per unit of production. This comparison makes the point again that a total approach to reengineering the laminate has to be considered to achieve waste reduction and improvements in productivity.

Table 6. Material Cost Change

	Cost Per Pound	Costs Per Unit of Production
Gel coat	Up 10%	Down 40%
Glass	Up 40%	Up 17%
Resin	Up 7%	Down 52%

Arjay's approach to waste reduction and performance improvement appears to be successful. The methods and techniques used are straight forward and do not require disproportionate investments in time or money. They do, however, require a company wide approach that will challenge everyone in the manufacturing system to become involved in rethinking what is fast, expensive, and wasteful.

JOINING AND REPAIR
